

Individual Report on

Evaluation of Build Orientation Influence on the Surface Texture of SLS-Manufactured Nylon 11 Components Using Focus Variation Metrology

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Abstract

This investigation was conducted to address the critical challenge of high surface roughness in Selective Laser Sintering (SLS), which significantly impacts the functional performance and dimensional accuracy of additively manufactured parts. The primary objective was to evaluate how build orientation influences the resulting surface integrity of Nylon 11 components. To achieve this, two square plate specimens were fabricated in horizontal and vertical orientations. Surface characterization was performed using the Alicona G5 Infinite Focus system, utilizing non-contact focus variation microscopy to capture 3D topographic data.

The resulting datasets were analyzed in Mountains Map software to calculate areal texture parameters according to ISO 25178-2. The study found that the vertically printed specimen exhibited a 51% increase in arithmetic mean height (S_a), rising from 14.95 μm (horizontal) to 22.63 μm . Furthermore, the vertical orientation showed nearly double the maximum height (S_z) and a more negative skewness (S_{sk}), indicating deeper valleys and sharper peaks.

These results confirm that build orientation is a critical determinant of surface quality, vertical surfaces suffer more severely from the staircase effect and adhered powder particles. Consequently, optimizing orientation is essential for enhancing the surface finish and reliability of SLS components.

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1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM) has emerged as a transformative technology capable of producing complex, near-net-shape components without the geometric constraints of traditional subtractive methodologies [1]. Despite its exceptional design flexibility, parts produced via AM frequently suffer from adverse surface integrity, typically exhibiting high surface roughness. The resulting surface topography is a critical determinant of a component's overall functional performance, directly influencing dimensional accuracy, tribological behaviour, fatigue life, and corrosion resistance [2]. Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) is a prominent powder bed fusion technique that utilises a laser to selectively melt and fuse thermoplastic polymer powder layer by layer shown in figure 1. Although SLS enables the fabrication of highly intricate geometries without the need for support structures, the resulting components exhibit a characteristically high and complex intrinsic surface roughness [3]. This inherent roughness is governed by the presence of partially melted powder particles adhering to the component's outer surfaces, a phenomenon worsened by heat dispersion into the surrounding powder bed. Furthermore, the layer-wise fabrication process induces a staircase effect, particularly on non-vertical and semi-horizontal planes, which increases the surface roughness [4].

Figure 1: Schematic representation of Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) process showing layer-wise powder fusion [12].

Accurate surface metrology is thus required for evaluating and refining AM processes. Earlier, surface roughness has been quantified using two-dimensional (2D) contact stylus profilometry to determine linear profile parameters such as the arithmetic mean roughness, R_a , according to ISO 4287 [5]. However, AM surfaces lack a consistent lay and feature extremely high local variability, meaning that 2D profiles routinely fail to capture sufficient spatial data to adequately represent the true surface. Furthermore, tactile styli can physically smooth or scratch relatively soft polymer surfaces, and they possess tip radii too large to fully penetrate the narrow, deep valleys that are characteristic of powder-based AM parts [1]. To achieve a more robust characterisation, three-dimensional (3D) areal surface texture analysis based on the ISO 25178 standard has become the preferred approach. Areal parameters, such as the arithmetic mean height (S_a), root mean square height (S_q), and maximum height (S_z), evaluate a wider field of view, thereby precisely accounting for the complex, stochastically distributed peaks, voids, and agglomerations inherent to AM surfaces [2].

To facilitate this comprehensive areal measurement without damaging delicate polymer surfaces, non-contact optical metrology methods are increasingly deployed. Among these, Focus Variation (FV) microscopy has proven particularly effective for AM parts, offering a robust method to measure both form and surface texture[6]. The operating principle of FV involves axially scanning the objective lens relative to the specimen, capturing a vertical stack of 2D images with a narrow depth of field. Advanced algorithms then calculate the local contrast or sharpness of each pixel across the image stack, assigning a specific Z-height to the plane of maximum focus to generate a precise 3D topographic map. The primary advantage of FV for AM metrology is its superior ability to capture high slope angles and re-entrant features while remaining comparatively resilient to the varying optical properties of rough surfaces [5]. The Alicona G5 Infinite Focus system exemplifies this technology, allowing for true-colour 3D measurements and relatively rapid acquisition times. Nevertheless, optical FV systems possess distinct limitations; regions with severe slopes, deep recesses, or oversaturated highly reflective plateaus can prevent the detector from capturing adequate reflected light, leading to data loss in the form of non-measured points [7,8]. Additionally, optical methods may suffer from measurement artifacts, such as volume scattering or focal ambiguity.

Recent academic literature has extensively investigated the metrological challenges and orientation dependencies of AM surfaces. Research in literature [1] demonstrated that build orientation significantly governs the extent of roughness; for instance, down-facing surfaces tend to accumulate more unmelted particles due to gravity and thermal diffusion, generating distinctly different arithmetic mean heights compared to top or side surfaces. Similarly, comparative metrology studies have examined the efficacy of optical and tactile devices in capturing these unique morphologies. One of the papers [2] highlighted that while FV systems are excellent for comprehensive areal analysis, they can struggle with surface reflectivity variations, resulting in non-measured points that must be carefully managed through proper post-processing and interpolation algorithms. Another paper [5] further verified that FV measurements of AM parts are generally robust concerning the Sa parameter, though changes in instrument settings like vertical resolution and illumination strongly influence the local repeatability error and point capture rates. Additionally, some literature [3] underscored that while tactile methods are highly reproducible, they systematically fail to detect undercuts and narrow gaps between SLS polymer particles, confirming the absolute necessity of optical FV microscopy for realistic 3D topography characterisation.

2. Methodology

2.1 Sample Preparation and Additive Manufacturing

The samples investigated in this study were fabricated using the Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) additive manufacturing process with Nylon 11 material. Two square plate specimens shown in figure 2 with dimensions of 36 mm \times 36 mm and a thickness of 5 mm were produced. The specimens were manufactured with different build orientations to investigate the influence of orientation on surface roughness characteristics. One sample was printed in a horizontal orientation while the second sample was printed in a vertical orientation.

Figure 2: Sample Print CAD geometry

Build orientation is a significant processing parameter in additive manufacturing because it directly affects the layer stacking direction, stair-stepping effect, powder adhesion behaviour, and thermal history of the component. These factors can strongly influence the resulting surface texture and dimensional quality of SLS-manufactured parts [1,4].

2.2 Measurement Instrument

Surface measurements were performed using the Alicona G5 Infinite Focus optical measurement system shown in figure 3. The Alicona G5 operates using the focus variation measurement principle, which combines optical microscopy with vertical scanning to generate three-dimensional surface topography data [6].

Figure 3: Alicona G5 system [6].

During measurement, the instrument vertically scans the sample surface while capturing a sequence of two-dimensional images at different focal distances shown in figure 4. The sharpness of each pixel within the image stack is evaluated, and the surface height is determined from the focal position corresponding to the maximum sharpness value. This enables reconstruction of the surface geometry with high vertical resolution. The Alicona G5 is suitable for additive manufacturing applications because it allows non-contact measurement of complex surfaces while avoiding damage to polymeric or delicate samples [5]. The system also enables measurement of both surface form and surface texture within a single setup. A 5× objective lens was used for all measurements in this investigation. According to the instrument specification data, the 5× configuration provides:

- Lateral sampling distance of 1.76 μm
- Minimum lateral resolution of 23.48 μm
- Best vertical resolution of 410 nm
- Field of view of 2858 $\mu\text{m} \times 2176 \mu\text{m}$
- Minimum measurable roughness (S_a) of 600 nm

These characteristics made the instrument suitable for analysing the relatively rough surfaces typically produced by SLS manufacturing as given in data sheet [6].

Figure 4: Focus variation system lab photo.

2.3 Measurement Procedure

The samples were mounted onto the measurement stage of the Alicona G5 Infinite Focus instrument. Measurements were conducted using the default scanning parameters supplied by the instrument software. The approximate scan duration for each measurement was 15 minutes. During the practical measurements, some challenges were encountered regarding positioning and selection of the scanning region. Obtaining a sufficiently large measurement area while maintaining correct alignment required repeated adjustment of the sample location and scan boundaries. Surface levelling and alignment procedures were applied before analysis to minimise the influence of sample tilt on the measured topography data [9]. The measurements generated three-dimensional areal surface datasets for both the horizontally and vertically printed specimens. The resulting datasets were exported and analysed using MountainsMap software.

2.4 Surface Analysis

Surface analysis was performed using the default analysis settings within MountainsMap software. The measured surfaces were levelled using least-square plane (LSPL) correction prior to evaluation. Surface texture parameters were calculated according to ISO 25178-2 areal surface texture standards [10]. The primary surface roughness parameters evaluated in this investigation included:

- Sa (arithmetical mean height)
- Sq (root mean square height)
- Sz (maximum surface height)
- Sp (maximum peak height)
- Sv (maximum valley depth)
- Ssk (skewness)
- Sku (kurtosis)

These parameters were selected because they provide quantitative information regarding surface amplitude characteristics and height distribution. Comparison of these values between the horizontally and vertically printed specimens enabled assessment of the influence of build orientation on SLS surface quality. An extracted surface profile was also generated from the measured topography data to provide additional visual interpretation of the surface morphology and layer-related features.

2.5 Sources of Measurement Uncertainty

Several factors may contribute to uncertainty within the measurement process. One limitation of optical focus variation systems is the presence of non-measured points, particularly in regions with steep slopes or poor optical reflection characteristics [5,8]. The measurement reports indicated the presence of non-measured points within the scanned datasets, which may influence the calculated surface parameters. Measurement uncertainty may also arise from:

- Sample positioning and alignment errors
- Surface contamination or adhered powder particles
- Variations in local reflectivity of the polymer surface
- Instrument optical resolution limitations
- Surface slope effects associated with layered additive manufacturing structures

In addition, the use of default software filtering and processing parameters may influence the calculated roughness values. However, consistent measurement conditions were maintained for both samples to ensure a fair comparative analysis between build orientations.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Surface Topography Measurements

Three-dimensional surface measurements were successfully obtained for both the horizontally and vertically printed Nylon 11 SLS specimens using the Alicona G5 Infinite Focus instrument. The measured datasets were processed within MountainsMap software using levelling and default filtering procedures in accordance with ISO 25178-2 surface texture analysis methods.

The scanned measurement areas for both samples were approximately 3 mm × 3 mm with a spatial sampling interval of approximately 1.76 μm. Surface topography maps and extracted profiles revealed clear differences in surface morphology between the two build orientations shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: 3D surface maps for (a) Vertical and (b) Horizontal orientation.

The horizontally printed specimen exhibited a comparatively smoother and more uniform surface texture. In contrast, the vertically printed specimen showed larger height variations and more pronounced surface irregularities. These differences are consistent with the layer-wise fabrication mechanism of the SLS process, where build orientation strongly influences the staircase effect and surface exposure to partially fused powder particles[1,4].

3.2 Surface Roughness Parameters

The calculated areal surface texture parameters for both specimens are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Areal Surface Texture parameters for measured specimens.

Parameter	Horizontal Build	Vertical Build
Sa (μm)	14.95	22.63
Sq (μm)	18.35	28.48
Sp (μm)	69.60	113.4
Sv (μm)	71.23	171.5
Sz (μm)	140.8	284.9
Ssk	-0.205	-0.530
Sku	2.660	3.548

The average surface roughness value (S_a) for the vertically printed specimen was significantly greater than that of the horizontally printed specimen. The vertical sample produced an S_a value of $22.63 \mu\text{m}$ compared to $14.95 \mu\text{m}$ for the horizontal sample, representing an increase of approximately 51%. Similarly, the S_q parameter increased from $18.35 \mu\text{m}$ to $28.48 \mu\text{m}$ for the vertically printed surface. The larger roughness values observed in the vertical build orientation indicate a rougher and more irregular surface morphology. This behaviour can be attributed to the orientation of deposited layers relative to the measured surface [1]. In vertically printed parts, the side surfaces are formed through successive layer boundaries, producing a stronger staircase effect and increased surface waviness [4]. Conversely, the horizontal sample surface was largely parallel to the powder bed plane, resulting in smoother layer consolidation and reduced height variation. The S_z parameter, representing maximum surface height variation, showed the largest difference between the two specimens. The vertically printed sample exhibited an S_z value of $284.9 \mu\text{m}$, approximately double the value measured for the horizontally printed sample ($140.8 \mu\text{m}$). This indicates the presence of deeper valleys and higher peaks on the vertically printed surface. The S_v value for the vertical sample was particularly high at $171.5 \mu\text{m}$, suggesting the existence of significant depressions or void-like surface features. These may result from partially sintered powder removal, uneven fusion between layers, or localised shrinkage effects during cooling [3].

3.3 Surface Height Distribution

The skewness parameter (S_{sk}) was negative for both samples, indicating that the surface height distributions were dominated by valleys rather than peaks [11]. The vertically printed sample showed a more negative skewness value (-0.530) compared to the horizontal sample (-0.205), suggesting a greater prevalence of deep valleys and irregular depressions.

The kurtosis parameter (S_{ku}) also differed between the samples. The horizontal sample exhibited an S_{ku} value of 2.660 , which is close to a normal surface height distribution. However, the vertically printed sample produced a higher S_{ku} value of 3.548 , indicating a surface with sharper peaks and deeper valleys. This suggests a more non-uniform and complex surface texture structure for the vertically printed specimen. These results indicate that build orientation influences not only average roughness amplitude but also the statistical distribution of surface features.

Figure 6: Height distribution curves for horizontal orientation.

3.4 Surface Profile Analysis

The extracted surface profile from the horizontally printed specimen, shown in figure 7 (a), demonstrated relatively stable height variation with moderate peak-to-valley differences across the scanned length. The profile showed periodic surface features associated with the layer-based manufacturing process. In comparison, the vertically printed specimen, shown in figure 7 (b), exhibited significantly larger fluctuations in surface height and more abrupt transitions between peaks and valleys. This behaviour further supports the quantitative roughness results and confirms the increased influence of the staircase effect in the vertical orientation [4]. The measured surfaces also contained non-measured points, as identified by the software. These regions may occur due to optical shadowing, steep local slopes, or insufficient reflected light reaching the detector. Although these missing data points may slightly affect parameter accuracy, the overall trends between the two orientations remained clearly distinguishable [8].

Figure 7: 2D extracted profile for (a) Horizontal and (b) Vertical orientation.

3.5 Suitability of Alicona G5 for Additive Manufacturing Surface Measurement

The Alicona G5 Infinite Focus system proved suitable for the evaluation of SLS-manufactured polymer surfaces. The non-contact measurement method avoided physical interaction with the relatively soft Nylon 11 specimens while enabling high-resolution three-dimensional surface acquisition. The focus variation principle was effective for capturing the rough and scattering surfaces commonly produced by powder bed fusion processes [5]. The instrument also enabled rapid acquisition of areal topography data over comparatively large measurement regions.

However, several limitations were observed during the investigation. Selection and alignment of the measurement region required careful adjustment, particularly when attempting to scan larger surface areas. The presence of non-measured points additionally highlighted limitations associated with steep local geometries and optical accessibility [8]. Despite these limitations, the Alicona G5 provided sufficient measurement capability to clearly distinguish the influence of build orientation on SLS surface quality. The results obtained in this investigation demonstrate that optical areal surface metrology is a valuable tool for characterising additively manufactured components and assessing process-induced surface variations.

4. Conclusion

This investigation evaluated the influence of build orientation on the surface texture of SLS-manufactured Nylon 11 components using focus variation optical metrology. Areal surface measurements obtained from the Alicona G5 Infinite Focus system and analysis in accordance with ISO 25178-2 provided a quantitative comparison between horizontally and vertically printed specimens.

The results demonstrated a clear dependence of surface roughness on build orientation. The vertically printed specimen exhibited consistently higher roughness values across all evaluated parameters, including Sa, Sq, Sz, Sp, and Sv. Sa increased from 14.95 μm for the horizontal build to 22.63 μm for the vertical build, indicating a substantial deterioration in surface quality. This trend was also reflected in the extreme height parameters, where the vertical sample showed significantly larger peak-to-valley variations, confirming the stronger influence of the staircase effect and layer boundary exposure.

Statistical surface descriptors further reinforced these findings. Both surfaces displayed negative skewness, indicating valley-dominated height distributions; however, the more negative skewness and higher kurtosis values in the vertically built sample indicated a more irregular surface with deeper depressions and sharper peak features. This highlights that build orientation affects not only average roughness magnitude but also the overall surface height distribution.

The Alicona G5 Infinite Focus system proved effective for capturing and differentiating these surface characteristics. Its non-contact focus variation principle enabled high-resolution areal reconstruction of relatively rough polymer surfaces without physical damage. However, the presence of non-measured points and sensitivity to steep surface slopes introduced measurable limitations, requiring careful interpretation of the resulting datasets.

The study confirms that build orientation is a critical parameter governing surface integrity in SLS additive manufacturing. Optical areal metrology using focus variation techniques provides a reliable and practical approach for characterizing such surfaces, although attention must be given to data completeness and optical accessibility limitations during analysis.

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